

Supporting Information

Comprehensive biodegradation analysis of chemically modified poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) materials with different crystal structure

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Figure S1 FTIR spectra for the studied films – 0.5% of the free-radical initiator.

Figure S2 FTIR spectra for the studied films – 1% of the free-radical initiator.

Figure S3. Macroscopic photographs of the extruded PHB and chemically modified PHB films before and after specific biodegradation periods in the soil environment (soil burial test, 55% soil humidity, 25°C).

Figure S4. Soil burial tests at 55% soil humidity and 25°C for PHB in powder, extruded and chemically modified forms – 0.5% of the free-radical initiator.

Figure S5. Soil burial tests at 55% soil humidity and 25°C for PHB in powder, extruded and chemically modified forms – 1% of the free-radical initiator.

Figure S6. Fluorescence micrographs of PHB-degrading microbial consortia in the process of degrading PHB (green – live).

Figure S7. Diversity of the bacterial community on the surfaces of the materials at 3 intervals, described by Shannon and Simpson indexes; (CNT-soil, A – extruded PHB, B – 0.5L, C – 0.5L/0.5MA, D – 0.5L/1MA, G – 1L, I – 1L/1MA, K – 1L/2L).

Figure S8. Scatter plot of principal component analysis, applying Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) and Bray-Curtis dissimilarity to highlight resemblances between the bacterial communities on the investigated samples; (CNT-soil, A – extruded PHB, B – 0.5L, C – 0.5L/0.5MA, D – 0.5L/1MA, G – 1L, I – 1L/1MA, K – 1L/2L).